

1973

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
seventeenth annual report

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is a private operating foundation incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960, in 1967, and again in 1971 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling eighteen million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts its work through directly administered programs as well as grants to and contracts with other appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

17th annual report

for the year ending June 30, 1973

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¹ Dr. Brooks succeeded Mr. Humphry November 11, 1972.

² Mr. Lagueux joined the staff August 14, 1972.

³ Dr. Liebaers joined the staff May 1, 1973.

introduction the year 1972-73

Those of us who view the work of libraries and librarians from something of a distance on occasion see trends that are perhaps less apparent to librarians themselves. In spite of the financial stresses and strains imposed upon the libraries of this country, there seems to be much movement forward. There seems to be progress in cooperative efforts. There seems to be improvement in management and administration. There seems to be advancement in the development of cost-beneficial automated procedures. Most important of all, there appears to be a better understanding in this country of the importance, even the absolute necessity, of a strong library system. Equally significant, there seems to be improvement in the status and role of librarians. They are not yet receiving the economic rewards that would be appropriate, but the importance of librarians and library services to the nation seems to be gaining a recognition that has not been apparent before.

Perhaps these developments are not yet what they seem, but we are hopeful. One may cautiously say that the past year has not been the best of times, but certainly not the worst of times. Progress has been made, and in this we hope that the work of the Council on Library Resources has been helpful.

FRED C. COLE
President

national library services

In the seventeen years of its existence, the Council on Library Resources has spent well over nineteen million dollars for activities and programs intended to assist libraries. There has been great variance in the titles these activities and programs have carried, but an essential element in almost every project has been its capacity to enhance the effectiveness, efficiency, and economy of operations in libraries.

An important way that these may be attained is through the development of central sources, governmental or private, which can make available to all libraries services that all libraries need and thereby eliminate many of the procedures that are replicated in each. In recent years the Council has been giving increased attention to this aspect of its work.

In its *14th Annual Report* (1970) under "Assisting the Development of a National Library System," the Council discussed at some length what it considered then to be an "optimum" U. S. library situation: centralized cataloging, a single national data base in machine-readable form, and an efficient communication network serving all the nation's libraries.¹ Today, as then, the "optimum" lies in the future. However, the Council's encouragement of and assistance to such related programs as Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC), Retrospective Conversion of Cataloging Records (RECON), the National Serials Data Program (NSDP), Standard Serial Number (SSN), and Cataloging in Publication (CIP), and to a variety of cooperative groupings of libraries and information centers are helping to bring this distant vision more clearly into focus.

¹ XIV:17-26. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example to the *Fourteenth Annual Report*, pages 17-26.

**National
Serials
Data
Program**

A major responsibility in large research libraries is control of the thousands of serial publications which are issued each year. These periodicals are the major timely source of the new ideas and information so important to scholars in all fields. Obscure sources, changing titles, and difficulties in claiming missing issues make the handling of serials complicated indeed. The National Serials Data Program (NSDP)—a cooperative effort of the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and the National Agricultural Library—represents an attempt to provide a solution to this difficult library problem.² Now in its sixth year, NSDP has proceeded steadily toward the creation of an initial file of those serials presently cataloged by the three libraries—approximately 14,000 titles annually. Two other files are in the developmental stage: a Corporate Entry Authority File, and a file of holdings records accessible by International Standard Serial Number and key title. The goal is a national machine-readable bibliographic data base for all serials which will uniquely identify each title, supply important cataloging information to all libraries, and permit the uniform transfer of data on serials.

In 1972-73 the Council supplemented an already sizable commitment to the National Serials Data Program with a new grant and continued professional assistance; one Council staff member devotes over half his time to the project. It is expected that in the future the necessary funding will be provided by the federal government.

**Cataloging
in
Publication**

Access to library holdings is through the catalog, usually a card catalog, which in any of its forms lists publications generally by author, title, and subject. Maintenance of these catalogs in the United States depends largely on basic catalog cards prepared by the Library of Congress (LC) and made available to all libraries wishing to purchase them. This system, which has operated for 70 years, not only contributes to standardization in cataloging but also provides a measure of quality as well as great savings of time and money to U. S. libraries.

Despite (or perhaps because of) these advantages, there were those who felt that the system could be improved by having the cataloging information available in the book itself instead of on a separate card. Such a system would eliminate a noticeable time lag in receipt by a library of the information needed before a book can be made available to the user, and would also lower costs appreciably. Under the system it would no longer be necessary to order cards individually, await shipment, check their receipt, compare with the book to assure identity, and prepare payment.

A preliminary Council-supported experiment called Cataloging in Source was carried out by the Library of Congress and U. S. publishers in 1958-59.³ A decision was made by the Library not to continue the

² XII:14-15; XVI:20-21.

³ II:15-18; IV:24-25; X:18.

program beyond the period of the grant. Ten years later, however, the growing number of books to be cataloged by LC and the time lag in providing cataloging information to libraries, together with the enormous increase in orders for the LC cards, created a condition which compelled the reevaluation of the 1959 project. In response to requests from publishers, libraries, and the Librarian of Congress, the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities in 1971 provided two-year funding for a renewal of the program, now called Cataloging in Publication (CIP).⁴ The grant was made with the understanding that if the trial met with success the work would be continued thereafter as a regular part of the Library's program. (An appropriation was authorized by Congress in the summer of 1973.)

CIP has succeeded in large part because of the willingness of the nation's publishers and the Library of Congress to resolve what seemed insurmountable problems during the earlier experience. There are presently over 400 publishers participating in the program, and as of May 1973 more than 17,000 titles had been published containing cataloging information. Approximately 55 percent of the U. S. book trade production is cooperating with CIP, with this figure expected to climb to 75 percent before the year ends. Preliminary planning is now under way to expand CIP to include selected federal documents.

**Major
MARC
users**

Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC), initiated by a series of CLR grants to the Library of Congress, is, we believe, the single most important contribution to date in the pursuit of national (or universal) bibliographic control.⁵ Consortia of libraries and those larger research libraries building automated systems use the MARC records as a primary source of authoritative cataloging copy in machine-readable form. However, because MARC coverage is not yet sufficiently comprehensive, the developing systems are understandably attempting to fill the gap by themselves creating the unavailable records. This is occurring essentially without national coordination or direction and could result in the expenditure of large sums on systems which are unable to communicate with each other. In an effort to enhance the compatibility and usefulness of the bibliographic records created in these diverse systems, the Council this year initiated a series of meetings for the nation's major MARC users and representatives of the Library of Congress. The progress toward agreements on acceptable standards in these working level meetings is encouraging.

**Reports
on
RECON**

Retrospective Conversion (RECON), the Library of Congress' CLR-supported program of converting pre-MARC monograph cataloging information to machine-readable form, was the subject of two printed reports in 1972-73: *RECON Pilot Project* and *National Aspects of Creat-*

⁴ XVI:21-22.

⁵ X:29-30, 41-42; XI:11-12; XII:13-14; XIII:12-17; XIV:22-24.

ing and Using MARC/RECON Records. General conclusion of the two: It is imperative that steps be taken to develop a national plan for conversion of retrospective catalog records to MARC format. "Although it seems impossible to prevent all duplication of effort, it is within the realm of possibility to keep that duplication to a minimum and to achieve a high degree of compatibility among records converted in different places."⁶

Setting national standards

The American National Standards Institute's (ANSI) Sectional Committee Z-39, concerned with setting standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities, has been receiving funding from the Council and the National Science Foundation since 1965.⁷ Council staff members assist several of its subcommittees, including the one responsible for developing the U. S. standard for serial numbers (SSN), which was promulgated and accepted in 1970.

However, standardization of serial numbers in the United States is only the first step toward achieving final clarity. Today scholars of every discipline depend, for current information in their fields, on journals issued in a variety of languages by publishers all over the world. Thus the problem remains unresolved unless there exists a universally accepted standard for identifying serials, no matter what their country of origin. The International Standards Organization, of which ANSI is a component, is the body responsible for adopting such a standard; it has this year circulated to its constituent members for final balloting a proposed International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) based on Z-39's Standard Serial Number and meeting all U. S. requirements. Here, too, CLR staff participation was an important factor as the international library community made an essential move in a most complex situation.

Council program officers have also served ANSI in such diverse ways as providing technical assistance during the development of the International Serials Data System, the group charged with the assignment of ISSNs to the various national centers for local application; assisting in the development of an identification code for journal articles; and chairing a subcommittee charged with setting standards for the advertising of microfiche.

Public policy and the library

The Council participated in and partially supported a June 8, 1973, meeting in New York City on "The Impact of Changing Public Policy on Libraries and the Free Flow of Information." Sponsored by the National Book Committee and the Aspen Program on Communications and Society, the one-day conference resulted in a healthy dialogue among the 35 participants, who discussed potential cuts in public support of libraries from a variety of vantage points. Several

⁶ RECON Working Task Force, *National Aspects of Creating and Using MARC/RECON Records* (Washington: Library of Congress, 1973).

⁷ XV:21-22.

lay conferees stressed the need for a better understanding at the local level of the types of services provided by libraries and a recognition of their importance.

A list of CLR national library services projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for the publication of a new compilation of federal and state legislation to supplant a long obsolete second edition of <i>American Library Laws</i> , and for biennial supplements. The fourth supplement covering 1969-70 was published in the fall of 1971. Receipts from sales will be used for a fourth edition and supplements. [\$10,500 – 1963]	\$ ———	\$ ———
Library of Congress , further support of the National Serials Data Program. (Supplements \$105,000 provided by the Library of Congress, National Library of Medicine, and National Agricultural Library.)	20,000	20,000
Library of Congress , for a continuation of the RECON project aimed at converting 85,000 (1968-69) English language monograph titles and 5,000 other selected titles to machine readable form. [\$200,959 – 1970]	—————	—————
National Book Committee, Inc. , to support a one-day conference in New York on the aggregate impact of present public policies on libraries and the free flow of books and periodicals.	5,000	3,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as a matching grant to be used with NEH grant of \$200,000 to launch the Library of Congress' new program of Cataloging in Publication. [\$200,000 – 1971]	—————	—————
United States Book Exchange , to enable the Exchange to restore its staff to approximately the 1969 level in order to maintain services to libraries. [\$48,450 – 1971]	(\$42)	8,408
University of North Carolina , to underwrite a portion of the expenses of the American National Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z-39 and its subcommittees as they work toward standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities. [\$61,275 – 1970]	—————	5,425
NATIONAL LIBRARIES TOTALS, 1972-73	\$ 24,958	\$ 36,833

automation and networks

Almost from its inception the Council on Library Resources has supported the application of the computer and related technology to library processes. The first project thus undertaken was in 1958, when a grant was made to the National Library of Medicine for the improvement of its *Current List of Medical Literature*, then the world's largest service in terms of quantity of material indexed for the literature of a special subject.⁸ The project eventually resulted in MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System), one of the best known computer-supported systems of the present day. Within the past two years MEDLARS has been made available on-line (MEDLINE) to medical researchers in all parts of the country.

In the six years that followed that first award the Council made grants of close to a million dollars for programs that ranged the field of computerization in libraries as it then existed. Support was given to projects in automatic indexing, searching law by computer, experimental application to the maintenance of serial records, research into the library of the future, computer-controlled typographic composi-

⁸ II:12-13; VII:9-11.

tion, optical scanning, and many others—all important and necessary activities in the effort to promote a coordinated approach to the application of automation to library processes. Then, as noted in the preceding section, came the development of Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC) at the Library of Congress, in our judgment the single most significant factor in the successful use of computerization in libraries. MARC provided what had heretofore been lacking, a standardized format for the transmission of bibliographic data. It was, and is, a powerful standardizing influence in the handling of bibliographic records in machine-readable form. Without it, or something like it, the interchange of bibliographic data or the construction of library networks would be impossible.

In the last five years the Council has greatly increased its rate of spending on automation projects. In addition to the development of MARC, there were some important changes in attitudes and conditions which made this enlarged activity possible:

- Greater understanding generally of the problems involved.
- Broader experience to draw upon in judging which approaches to solutions appear most promising.
- The advent of a small but growing body of individuals skilled in both library and systems work.
- Some efforts among hardware manufacturers to develop equipment suitable for efficient library applications.
- The emergence of a sufficient body of work in both theory and application on which viable library systems can be built.

In 1972-73 the Council committed \$297,000 to four new programs in this area. Grants to previously funded and still active automation projects amount to an additional \$1.3 million. During this year the Council has focused its funds and energies on programs which appear to offer reasonable solutions to current problems.

**Ohio
College
Library
Center**

The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), which has been quite successful in putting the computer to work for libraries not only in Ohio but in other sections of the country, received a new CLR grant in 1973. Now a regional consortium of approximately sixty Ohio library members and approximately that number of affiliates, OCLC was funded in its early developmental phase by the U. S. Office of Education (OE) and by the Center's original membership of 49 academic libraries. Last year the Council and OE shared the developmental cost; in calendar year 1973 the Council alone provides this support.⁹ Operational aspects of the OCLC system have been financed thus far by fees received from user institutions and by State of Ohio funds on behalf of its academic libraries.

⁹ XVI:18.

Among OCLC's accomplishments to date are:

- A method to provide bibliographic data in the catalog card format required by each of its member libraries.
- Efficient search keys for bibliographic searches.
- The first successful use of cathode-ray terminals designed specifically for library work.

Its on-line union catalog and shared cataloging systems have been operational since August 1971, and OCLC is well along in its developmental work toward implementing two of the other five subsystems planned: serials control and the acquisitions module of the technical processing system. The other scheduled subsystems are for interlibrary loan communication, remote catalog access and circulation control, and retrieval by subject.

**NELINET
now on-line
to OCLC
computer**

A related grant went to the New England Library Information Network (NELINET) in 1972 to study the feasibility of transferring the OCLC computer-based bibliographic system to other groups of libraries.¹⁰ Dartmouth College, the NELINET demonstration library in testing the transferability, reported that it could effect considerable savings through an OCLC tie-in. The project was such a satisfactory demonstration that NELINET is now on-line to the OCLC computer in Columbus and, along with at least eight other groups, is looking toward future replication of the OCLC system.

**Automation
in large
university
libraries**

Although OCLC is a promising development, it does not now provide all the needed answers, particularly to the problems faced by very large academic research libraries. Representative of this category are the University of Chicago and Stanford University, for whose automation projects major funding is provided by the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and the Council. Chicago and Stanford, like most large universities possessing computer centers, are committed to using the campus facility and must design their software within the constraints imposed by other university activities. OCLC, on the other hand, has a computer dedicated to its needs and thus is free to develop its entire software package without reference to conflicting demands from other users.

**University
of Chicago
system**

At Chicago, the central design factor is the very complex integration of all the files related to the management of books and serials in a library. General purpose software packages did not prove adequate as first tried, so today Chicago is employing two specially acquired com-

¹⁰ XVI:18.

mercial packages. Campus administrative applications are already running under these monitors, and the library system is designed to run in harmony with them, with programs for the library applications written in-house. The Chicago system is to be fully compatible with MARC and hence with the other systems supported by the Council.¹¹

The overall design for the Chicago system is now complete. Bibliographic and processing data records are to be created once and then shared in a multiplicity of uses, with additions made to the records as needed. As a book goes through the processes of selection, ordering, receipt, and processing, an account of its location and status is maintained; this makes it available to the reader even before processing is complete. Ultimately, the permanent records are used for bibliographic control and searching.

**Stanford's
BALLOTS**

Stanford's BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-Sharing System) is another instance of the Council's coming to the aid of a previously federally funded project at a critical juncture. The joint CLR-NEH grant was made because U. S. Office of Education support came to an end just as the system design was close to completion and first-stage implementation.¹² Of the 11 modules planned, Stanford has now completed three: (1) its MARC module based on conversion of MARC cataloging tapes for use in the order division and catalog department, (2) the In-Process File module for use throughout technical processing where MARC records are available, and (3) the Catalog Data File module for on-line cataloging of MARC records. With the continued help of the CLR-NEH grant, BALLOTS is moving ahead toward the ultimate goal: the use of machine-readable and machine-maintained files for purchasing and cataloging materials, for updating and retrieving bibliographic records, for circulation control, and for on-line bibliographic searches.

**Bucknell
University
system**

A recent grant to Bucknell University complements those to OCLC, Chicago, and Stanford. That relatively small institution has been one of the leaders in making access to the computer available to all students and faculty for use in regular course work. The intention now is to extend such access so that users may search the library's bibliographic files. Because computer storage capability is limited, only 25,000 of the library's 200,000 bibliographic records have been available on-line. The Council grant will make it possible for the entire bibliographic file to be put on-line. In addition, a search capability, which at present is for author-title and Library of Congress number, will be expanded to include subject as well.

¹¹ XVI:19.

¹² XVI:18-19.

**Project
Intrex**

The Council's long-term investment in support of the highly sophisticated and ambitious Project Intrex at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T.) has come to an end with the demonstration of the system's technical feasibility.¹³ The Council and its Advisory Committee on Intrex have recommended that M.I.T. consider the possibility of turning to government and industry for support of practical utilization of an effective but expensive specialized system.

**Washington
State
Network**

The Council made several grants in 1973 to promote the sharing of resources in state and regional environments. A grant to the Washington State Library is for continued development of its state-wide computerized library network, with the funds earmarked for development of specifications for the network's on-line acquisitions module. The Washington State Network's mandate reads: "to promote increased sharing of resources by libraries, particularly of different kinds and with different area jurisdictions . . . and to expand the availability of library materials to every resident in the state."

**SLICE
receives
second
grant**

Another grant in regional sharing was to the Southwestern Library Association, the Council's second in support of the year-old Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE).¹⁴ The funds will enable the six-state SLICE (Texas, Louisiana, Oklahoma, Arkansas, New Mexico, and Arizona) to further its development of a systematic regional plan for increasing and stimulating the sharing of library resources, services, and expertise within the region. Design requirements and cost data will be developed for various alternative types of regional bibliographic networks, with emphasis on broadening the use of MARC records. In addition to its \$25,000 annual funding from the Council over the next two years, the SLICE office has been assured of \$4,000 per year from each of the six state library agencies.

**Council's
consulting
role**

Grant-making and monitoring are only one aspect of the Council's involvement in automation and networks projects. In another equally important function CLR systems staff members meet with and advise numerous institutions and consortia who request this counsel relative to their current automation activities and planning for the future. Such meetings are mutually beneficial, on the one hand providing those who solicit it with advice from an unprejudiced source, and, on the other, helping the Council to stay abreast of developments in automation.

¹³ XVI:19-20.

¹⁴ XVI:22.

A list of CLR automation and networks projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Bucknell University , for an experiment in which students will use already available terminals to search on-line the entire data base of the library.	\$ 28,000	\$ 6,500
Massachusetts Institute of Technology (Project Intrex), to continue a program of controlled experiments aimed at establishing characteristics and specifications for future library information and retrieval systems. [\$400,000 – 1972]	—————	50,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds toward a \$650,000 combined Council-NEH grant to the Stanford University Libraries to complete the basic development of the BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Libraries On-Line Time-Sharing) system and bring it to operational status. [\$325,000 – 1972]	—————	—————
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds for \$800,000 joint Council-NEH grant to the University of Chicago for development and operational testing of a data management system at the library. [\$400,000 – 1970]	—————	—————
New England Board of Higher Education , to test the transferability of the Ohio College Library Center's computer-based bibliographic system to other libraries. [\$53,589 – 1972]	—————	24,000
New England Board of Higher Education , for a technical and user audit of the New England Library Information Network cataloging support sub-system. [\$24,000 – 1971]	—————	—————
Ohio College Library Center , assistance toward purchase of equipment for the development of a computerized regional library system. [\$14,113 – 1970]	(\$1)	1,199
Ohio College Library Center , to aid in developing and activating a computer-based, on-line shared cataloging system. [\$75,000 – 1972]	—————	55,000
Ohio College Library Center , toward further development of its computerized regional system.	194,000	85,000
Revision of the Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries (CLR-administered), to Becker and Hayes, Inc., from CLR royalties received from John Wiley & Sons, Inc., publisher of first edition, originally prepared under 1965 CLR grant to the Regents of the University of California.	—————	4,000
Southwestern Library Association , to further interlibrary cooperation and planning in the states of Arizona, Arkansas, Louisiana, New Mexico, Oklahoma, and Texas. Entitled Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE), the project will provide centralized, development, and coordination of educational and other library activities in the region. [\$25,000 – 1972]	—————	7,750

Southwestern Library Association , toward further development of the SLICE program.	50,000	11,600
Washington State Library , supporting partial development of Washington State's computerized statewide network.	25,000	20,000
AUTOMATION AND NETWORK TOTALS, 1972-73	\$296,999	\$265,049

the academic library

College and university library budgets have grown in size over the past twenty years at approximately the same rate as the budgets of other academic departments. They have remained a relatively constant 4.2 percent of educational expenditures and for the most part have reflected additional students enrolled and basic dollar inflation. What they do not in many cases take into account are the strains imposed by increases in cost and number of publications and the escalating costs of personnel.

Earlier sections of this report have dealt with Council-supported projects designed to enhance efficiency and economy of operation by encouraging the development of centralized services and the application of computer technology to library processes. All of these programs, no matter where they are situated, are intended to assist the academic library to make the most of its insufficient funds. In a more particularized effort to help, the Council several years ago began a series of projects in management, some of which are discussed in the pages that follow.

But it takes more than good management techniques and procedures to make a good library. Students and faculty alike must be aware of the benefits its proper use can bring, and for this the library itself must take much responsibility. Here too the Council has initiated programs which, it is hoped, will have significant impact on the use of the academic library by its constituents.

Current grants supporting automation and network projects on the nation's campuses are discussed in the preceding section. Nine programs relating to management and to the undergraduate library received Council grants in 1972-73, with twenty-one similar projects previously funded also active during the year.

MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING

The need for planning and improved management in academic libraries has long been of concern to the Council. Higher education's rapid growth since World War II and its accompanying demands for more materials and services have combined to exert considerable pressure on librarians. In an article entitled "The Changing Role of Directors of University Libraries" (March 1973 *College & Research Libraries*), Arthur McAnally and Robert Downs advanced the theory that such pressure is a factor in the "extraordinarily high rate of change" among senior librarians in the past few years, including quite a number of early retirements. To reverse this trend, the article urged "better plan-

ning, improved budgeting techniques, and the introduction of new organizational patterns.”¹⁵ It is hoped that the CLR-funded studies and projects discussed below will be steps in this direction.

Economic factors analyzed

In an attempt to help librarians, as well as the administrators to whom they report, place accelerating library budgets into proper perspective, the Council has supported a major economic study of academic libraries, publication of the report, and its distribution to presidents of most of the nation’s universities and colleges.¹⁶ William J. Baumol and Matityahu Marcus performed the study under a grant to Mathematica, Inc., and their report, *Economics of Academic Libraries*, has been published by The American Council on Education.

The authors’ analysis of such quantifiable variables in academic library operations as book expenditures, total library expenditures, salaries, volumes added, nonprofessional staff, and expenditures per student for the period 1950-69 showed a sufficient constancy in their growth patterns to justify the conclusion “that the observed behavior of costs of library operations and of related activities cannot be considered a chance occurrence.” They point out, further, that the cost increases are a “direct consequence of the association between the amount of human effort employed and the range of library services that can be offered.”

It is the Council’s hope, as it is the authors, “that the results of [the] analysis will prove helpful at a number of levels. They can be used by individual librarians in making plans for their own institutions, by college and university administrators in anticipating the future fiscal needs of their libraries and evaluating the financial consequences of decisions on overall institutional policy, and by organizations representing librarians in making their case for the resources they need and determining lines of research that will be most useful in planning for the future.”¹⁷

Office of University Library Management Studies

The Council-supported Office of University Library Management Studies within the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) continues a close working relationship with individual libraries participating in its Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP) while at the same time it broadens its management information and clearinghouse responsibilities to the academic library community.¹⁸ MRAP, a program for understanding and evaluating library management practices, is a starting point for the individual library to begin an ongoing process of critical evaluation—assisted by Office guidelines, training sessions, and direct counsel (upon request).

¹⁵ Arthur M. McAnally and Robert B. Downs, “The Changing Role of Directors of University Libraries,” *College & Research Libraries* 34 (March 1973).

¹⁶ XVI:10.

¹⁷ William J. Baumol and Matityahu Marcus, *Economics of Academic Libraries* (Washington: American Council on Education, 1973).

¹⁸ XVI:11

It is interesting to note that these self-studies have had an unexpected but important impact well beyond the involved libraries. In attempting to respond to some of the questions raised in the study process, the parent institutions have found it necessary on occasion to review their own goals, plans, patterns, and procedures and to take another, generally more realistic, look at the library *vis-à-vis* the rest of the academic community. This can only be helpful to libraries.

This year the Council made a new two-year grant of \$129,369 to ARL for continuation of the Office, originally funded by CLR in 1970. In its move toward implementing an expanded program, the Office has added the former director of the M.I.T. Model Engineering Library Program to the staff and has begun distribution of two new publications, *ARL Management Supplements* and *Occasional Papers*.

**Columbia
University
Libraries
Planning
Office**

A 1972 CLR-supported Booz, Allen & Hamilton study, "Organization and Staffing of the Libraries of Columbia University: A Case Study," is in process of implementation by the university. The university librarian has also received the additional title of "vice-president for information services" and a planning office for the libraries has been established under a Council grant.¹⁹ The office, now fully staffed, is concerning itself with five major areas: organizational definition, staffing description, operations planning, budgeting, and policy manual development. The published report of the study itself, which was sponsored by ARL in cooperation with the American Council on Education, will be available from Redgrave Information Resources Corporation later this year.

**Research and
development
at JUL**

Since 1969 the Council has supported a research and development unit in the Joint University Libraries (JUL) serving Vanderbilt University and Scarritt and George Peabody colleges in Nashville, Tennessee.²⁰ In the past year a systems specialist joined the staff, thus adding a new dimension to ongoing activities in such areas as personnel policies, administrative procedures, acquisitions statistics gathering, modification of the JUL accounting and management systems, and program budgeting concepts. An intensive self-study program entitled CO/OP (Comprehensive Organizational/Operational Planning) was initiated in the fall of 1972 and included among its first projects an assessment of the opinions of faculty users. The results of this survey and of others planned will provide the basic data for identifying needs and specifying concrete objectives for the JUL system.

**Cornell's
long-range
plan**

Cornell University's Council-supported program to develop a long-range plan and a planning method for its library system was completed during the year.²¹ The American Management Association's

¹⁹ XVI:10-11.

²⁰ XVI:11-12.

²¹ XVI:12.

Center for Planning, working with the library staff, developed a management-by-objectives system to fit the university's complex library organization. Because of the nature of the problem, the Cornell team avoided identifying specific projects and strategies but rather worked to develop a continuous planning module within the library administration. One aspect of the project was a successful in-house training program to acquaint Cornell librarians with the basic management-by-objectives technique. A 185-page report, "Development of a Long-Range Strategic Plan for a University Library" by William E. McGrath, is available through the ERIC system.²²

THE LIBRARY IN UNDERGRADUATE EDUCATION

College Library Program

"The library should be the keystone in the process of liberal education. It not only supports the programs in all the academic departments but is the principal means by which their teaching can be extended in depth or breadth. The instruction that can be given in the classroom is necessarily bounded by arbitrary time factors; there are theoretically no limits to the learning that can be obtained through a library.

"What is more important, the library can open the way for continuity between a student's college experience and his intellectual growth throughout his life. Continuing self-instruction is essential for successful living in an age of challenge to all concepts, and an individual who can use a library stands the best chance of meeting that challenge, in the face of ephemeral facts and instant ideologies.

"But the library cannot be merely a passive partner in the educational process. It must have its own positive program; it must have dynamic and imaginative leadership. However, optimum effectiveness can be obtained only by coordinated endeavor on the part of administration, faculty, and library staff, based upon clearly defined institutional policies."

When these paragraphs, part of an internal paper, were written late in 1968, little was being done on a wide basis, either by or for the profession, to help the undergraduate library achieve a more focal point in education. It was for this reason that the Council in 1969 initiated the College Library Program (CLP) and with the National Endowment for the Humanities established a joint \$1,400,000 fund from which matching grants could be made to individual colleges and universities whose proposed programs showed promise of achieving CLP's goal and meeting its standard.²³

Sixteen plans have been funded to date, six of them during the year covered by this report. Among the common threads running through all plans are: an assurance of interest and cooperation from administration and faculty, library budget increases sufficient to match the CLR-NEH grants, and the designation of new positions on library staffs. Of the 1972-73 grants:

²² William E. McGrath, *Development of a Long-Range Strategic Plan for a University Library: The Cornell Experience* (Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell University Libraries, 1973).

²³ XVI:12-13.

Davidson College is hiring a coordinator of library resources for its new extended studies program which requires all students to complete special projects annually. The coordinator will aid students with their reference work and advise faculty and students on the practicality of their special extended studies program. The coordinator will be assisted by three to five subject specialists chosen from among the emeritus professors of the college.

Hampden-Sydney College has the added incentive of a three-year-old independent study program aimed at "intensifying the students' intellectual curiosity . . . beyond the classroom" to broaden its library's usefulness. Key elements in its CLR-NEH program are the integration of library work with teaching and the upgrading of the library staff's professional qualifications through on-campus training courses.

Jamestown College is creating the position of coordinator of library utilization in an attempt to influence its faculty to consider library resources when developing curriculum. The coordinator will also draw on faculty expertise in the process of enlarging the library's collection.

Miles College's project, "Bridging the Student Library-Use Gap through Library Instruction," will coordinate instruction in the effective and efficient use of the library with the college curriculum. It is hoped that the program will encourage the habit of self-education both during and after students' academic years.

The University of Colorado plan has as its focus the involvement of faculty in the promotion of library usage by students. Subject specialists will work closely with departmental faculty both in curricular matters and in guiding students' bibliographic work.

The University of Richmond has developed a "Library-Faculty Partnership" program under which some faculty members will be selected each year to devote part of their time to specific library teaching duties. In addition, new emphasis will be placed on improving the quality and usefulness of the library's collection.

**Core
Collection
Project**

The Council's Core Collection Project, undertaken in cooperation with the Association of College and Research Libraries of the American Library Association, is now expected to be completed in the spring of 1974. The core collection will provide, in a book catalog, a list of approximately 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college should have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education. The information is being recorded on computer tape and the catalog will be produced from machine-readable records, thus facilitating its use for other purposes, including updating. The Council has supplemented its original grant of \$290,502 with a \$21,100

award made early this fiscal year to cover unanticipated computer and coding costs.²⁴

**Project
Intrex
Model
Library**

Massachusetts Institute of Technology's three years of experiments in developing a model engineering library as a component of Project Intrex have resulted in a variety of techniques expected to benefit academic libraries generally.²⁵ One of these is point-of-use instruction — packaged programs of audio-visual materials designed to assist the patron in the use of specialized library tools, e.g., *Chemical Abstracts*. Another significant undertaking is "Library Pathfinders," single sheet guides to published information in over 200 subject areas now available to other libraries through a commercial publishing house. Other aspects of the efforts to improve usage of libraries include exposing students and faculty to such nonprint media as film loops, movies, videotapes, audio tapes, microfiche, and the related equipment adapted for individual users. User attitudes reflect the acceptance of, and in many instances a preference for, the nonprint media.

Council support of the program ended June 30, and a smooth transition of the model library's programs into the regular operations of the Barker Engineering Library is under way.

A list of CLR academic library projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for development from machine-readable records of a catalog in book form of an approximately 40,000-title core collection that will constitute an acceptable minimum for the support of the average college instructional program of good quality. [\$290,502 — 1969]	\$———	\$ 43,643
American Library Association , to supplement funding of "Core Collection for College Libraries" project.	21,100	———
Association of Research Libraries (ARL) , toward establishment of an office of university library management studies within ARL to further the work initiated by the Council-sponsored Booz, Allen, & Hamilton management study. [\$130,000 — 1971]	———	25,000
Association of Research Libraries (ARL) , continued support of ARL Office of University Library Management Studies.	129,369	27,000
Columbia University , three-year support for establishment of a planning office within the University Libraries. [\$126,308 — 1972]	———	42,500

²⁴ XVI:14.

²⁵ XVI:20.

Cornell University Libraries , to conduct a pioneering effort in developing a long-range plan and a planning method for the Cornell library system. [\$23,930—1972]	(\$2,915)	16,015
David Kaser , director of Cornell University Libraries, to enable him to visit the library management units at Cambridge University and the University of Lancaster.	931	931
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , continuation of the Project Intrex Model Engineering Library. [\$71,000—1972]	—————	42,600
Mathematica, Inc. , for a study of the economics of university library operations. [\$25,000—1970; \$17,500—1971]	—————	5,500
Michigan State University , for publication of a directory of university extension library services at National University Extension Association and National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges member institutions. [\$1,602—1972]	—————	1,200
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds to inaugurate and continue the CLR-NEH College Library Program, requiring matching funds from recipients. 1973 recipients: Davidson, Hampden-Sydney, Jamestown , and Miles colleges—\$50,000 each; universities of Colorado (\$75,750) and Richmond (\$50,000). 1970-72 recipients: Brown and Howard universities—\$100,000 each; Hampshire and Jackson State colleges and Dillard, Eastern Michigan, North Carolina Central and Washington and Lee universities—\$50,000 each; Swarthmore College —\$40,000. [\$250,000—1969; \$200,000—1970; \$250,000—1972]	—————	—————
National Endowment for the Humanities , matching funds for a \$15,000 grant to State University of New York at Stony Brook in support of a faculty-student development team in history. [\$7,500—1970]	—————	—————
University of Colorado , to assist in the publication of <i>Academic Library Buildings: A Guide to Architectural Issues and Solutions</i> by Ralph Ellsworth. The grant made it possible for the book to be sold at a cost of under \$10 per copy. It was published in January 1973. [\$10,000—1972]	—————	—————
University of Lancaster (England), to support fundamental research on factors affecting the use of library service with the hope that appropriate findings will aid libraries to become more responsive to their constituencies. [\$37,500—1971]	—————	4,500
Vanderbilt University , in behalf of the Joint University Libraries of Nashville (Vanderbilt, George Peabody, and Scarritt), to establish a model research and development unit. [\$171,107—1969; \$89,475—1972]	—————	64,086
Wabash College , to increase the effectiveness of the college library by changing its concept from that of a storehouse of information to that of a workshop of the liberal arts. [\$50,000—1970]	—————	10,000
ACADEMIC LIBRARY TOTALS, 1972-73	\$148,485	\$282,975

Your Public Library Comes to Your Mailbox

Number 5

Manitowoc County Library System

the public library

The public library is a laboratory for some interesting activities sponsored by the Council today. Like the academic library, the public library has experienced continuing growth since World War II—it became a billion-dollar enterprise in 1972. And that growth has, of course, been accompanied by problems.

A major challenge to it lies in attempting to meet the needs of a changing society. According to the Public Library Association's March 1972 report, *A Strategy for Public Library Change*, jointly sponsored by the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities, public libraries "are on the threshold of renaissance . . ."—if they are prepared to respond to societal developments calling for those community services which the public library can best perform.²⁶ In 1972-73, the Council provided financial assistance to five projects designed to give the public librarian guidelines for fulfilling his particular challenge.

Public library and non- traditional study

Nontraditional, off-campus study in higher education has been an interest of the Council for several years. A staff member has served on the Commission on Non-traditional Study since its formation. And in 1971 the Council joined with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and the College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) in providing financial support to the Dallas (Texas) Public Library for its two-year program to investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study directed toward a college education.²⁷

In keeping with this interest, the Council has now joined with NEH and the U. S. Office of Education to support CEEB's newly established Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects. Basic goals of the new office are:

- To serve as catalyst and coordinator, helping to bring public libraries and local colleges and universities together to share

²⁶ Public Library Association, *A Strategy for Public Library Change* (Chicago: American Library Association, 1972).

²⁷ XVI:28.

their collective knowledge and skills in aiding independent learners.

- To establish a national clearinghouse of information on library experiences with independent study projects.
- To develop learning materials and study aids that will help librarians in advising and guiding the adult learner.
- To demonstrate ways in which the libraries' existing resources may be used by independent students.

**Dallas
Independent
Study
Project**

Meanwhile the Dallas Independent Study Project continues to focus on CEEB's College Level Examination Program (CLEP) which offers individuals who are unable or unwilling to attend regular class sessions an opportunity to receive academic credit on the basis of independent study and CLEP examination scores. The Dallas Public Library works closely with Southern Methodist University and other neighboring institutions of higher education.²⁸ The project director is confident that the program, with variations, will ultimately attain permanent status within the city's library and in many other public libraries as well.

**Books-by-Mail
Conference**

The May 1973 *Wilson Library Bulletin* featured a story entitled "Books by Mail—Sleeper of the '70s?"²⁹ Co-authored by Choong H. Kim, associate professor of library science at Indiana State University, and Irwin M. Sexton, director of the San Antonio (Texas) Public Library, it was an appropriate article to appear on the eve of a June 23 Las Vegas Conference on Books by Mail directed by these two articulate advocates of this approach to public library service. A modest Council grant helped make possible the conference, which was attended by almost 200 interested librarians. A 60-minute cassette tape with highlights of the conference's discussions will be sent to participants and also made available to interested persons.

The *Bulletin* article is based on the experience of the San Antonio Public Library which, with a CLR grant, began a Books by Mail project in 1968.³⁰ Upon completion of the grant and the trial experience it supported, Books by Mail was incorporated permanently into the regular San Antonio service program, where it continues to grow.

**Research
prior to
Los Angeles
branch
construction**

Another significant experiment is the Los Angeles Public Library's proposed use of socio-psychological measurements of community attitudes and values in determining types of buildings and programs desirable for branch libraries in three of its neighborhoods. A Council grant, in part matched by the Educational Facilities Laboratories, is

²⁸ *ibid*

²⁹ Choong H. Kim and Irwin M. Sexton, "Books by Mail—Sleeper of the '70s?" *Wilson Library Bulletin* 47 (May 1973).

³⁰ XII:24-25.

making possible a study to focus on the needs, goals, motivations, and concerns of the people living in the three neighborhoods—one black, one Spanish-speaking, one white middle class. Basic to the project is the collection of information through interviews with both library users and nonusers. The data thus derived will be coded and processed by the computer facilities of the Opinion Research Center at the University of California, Los Angeles, and will assist the libraries' architects and planners in their design work.

**Brooklyn's
public
information
program**

The need for readily available information about public services and programs is particularly acute in urban areas where there are many newcomers. These people, many of whom do not speak English well or even understand it, must have reliable information to guide them through the intricacies of an unfamiliar society. The requirement of other citizens for accurate and timely information is equally compelling. Believing that the public library branch is the logical source of such assistance, New York City mapped out a program for the purpose and, when previously promised federal financing became unavailable, committed more than four million dollars of its own funds toward its development. The Council had earlier agreed to provide up to \$300,000 as an indication of its interest in the program and the problem it was to deal with.³¹

Under the direction of the Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, the program will link the Brooklyn Public Library's 55 branches to a computerized data bank, and thus enable them to provide requested information, heretofore unavailable centrally, on a wide variety of services. Specially trained paraprofessionals, two to a branch, will join with librarians as information and referral delivery teams.

Municipal officials as well as librarians, in New York City and elsewhere, will follow the experiment with great interest to learn if, in addition to providing information, the program can serve to restore the public library to its former central position in urban neighborhoods.

A list of all CLR public library projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, Inc. , toward the establishment of citizens' information centers in Brooklyn's 55 branch libraries. Council funds will be used for the salary of personnel responsible for creating and maintaining the central data base. [\$300,000—1972]	\$ ———	\$ 35,000

³¹ XVI:27-28.

College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) , in support of the newly established Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects.	100,000	12,500
Indiana State University , partial funding of "Books by Mail Service" conference held June 23, 1973, in Las Vegas, Nevada.	1,500	1,000
Los Angeles Public Library , Council's portion of \$48,320 grant made in cooperation with Educational Facilities Laboratories, to enable the library to identify needs, goals, motivations, and concerns of three city neighborhoods so that branch programs and library buildings planned there can be developed that will make the library a more vital part of community life.	32,200	_____
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward CLR-NEH \$50,000 grant to Dallas (Texas) Public Library , enabling library to investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study toward achieving a two-year college education under CEEB's College Level Examination Program (CLEP). NEH provided a second grant of \$25,000 and CEEB also provided a grant of \$25,000. [\$25,000—1971]	_____	_____
PUBLIC LIBRARY TOTALS, 1972-73	\$133,700	\$ 48,500

microforms, reprography, and nonprint media

The Council has believed from its beginning that microforms and other reprographic processes have a significant role to play in enabling the library to improve its services while reducing costs. However, the conflict of promise and problems as they related to these processes was proving most discouraging to both librarians and commercial interests when the Council began its work in the mid-1950s. In an attempt to resolve the conflict the Council in its first twelve years expended approximately one-sixth of its program funds on projects aimed at overcoming the weaknesses of microfilm, the equipment used to read it, and the intellectual aids needed for efficient utilization of micropublication collections. By the late 1960s it had become clear that the size of the investment necessary to develop marketable equipment was beyond the capacity of an organization like the Council, with limited funds and unlimited responsibilities to libraries. At this same time,

fortunately, commercial enterprises began to show a sharpening of interest in the potential market supplied by libraries, and several large manufacturing and marketing organizations embarked on ambitious library microform projects.

**Monitor-
advocate
role**

This turn of events has resulted in the Council's assuming a new and perhaps more effective role as unofficial monitor and advocate of libraries *vis-à-vis* the industry in providing informed and, hopefully, unbiased consulting services. A CLR staff member devotes a large portion of his time to library microform problems through leadership and service on a number of working committees of relevant national organizations. As a result, the Council is increasingly called upon to provide counsel to individual institutions on microform matters.

**Microfiche
reader
testing**

At the present time two projects aimed at improving microfiche services are being administered by the Council: one to assist librarians to determine the suitability of microfiche readers, the other the development of an operational prototype of an automatic catalog card filming camera.

There are almost 200 different readers and reader/printers for microfiche on the market today; a potential purchaser who must choose among them often has only the manufacturers' claims to guide him in his selection. So that the buyer may make his decision on the basis of performance and the suitability of a particular device to his requirements, the Council is supporting and participating in the preparation of a booklet on reader selection and a special set of microfiche which will enable librarians to test microfiche readers effectively. The project is expected to be completed in the coming fiscal year and includes printing and distribution to libraries of a sizable number of booklets and microfiche.

**A new
catalog card
camera**

The catalog card camera, needed by librarians seeking to protect their catalogs against disaster and to provide inexpensive copies of their catalogs to others, has been developmentally tested at the University of Toronto Library under normal operating conditions. It has been modified in accordance with findings during that testing and will shortly be delivered to the University of Southern California Library for further experimentation. Developed by Mega Systems Design of Toronto under contract to CLR, the camera is to feature high resolution images, speed of about 100 cards per minute, reliable feeding of cards of varying thickness and physical condition, and high density recording on 16 mm. film.³²

³² XVI:42-43.

Information project at Governors State

The Council is supporting at Governors State University a nine-month pilot project which attempts to match the interests of its faculty and administrators with the National Technical Information Service's (NTIS) Selective Dissemination of Microfiche. During the grant period Governors State is expected to receive 8,135 NTIS documents on microfiche covering 130 categories and subcategories, and to make and distribute an estimated total of 23,660 microfiche copies in accordance with faculty members' stated interests. The amount of usage will provide answers both as to faculty members' interest in the NTIS materials and their willingness to use microfiche.

Videotaping ASIS meeting

A \$7,500 matching grant to the American Society for Information Science (ASIS) helped to test the usefulness of videotapes in broadening the impact of national meetings. All technical sessions of the 1972 ASIS Annual Meeting in Washington, D. C., were videotaped and the edited tapes made available to interested schools, local ASIS chapters, and related groups. A marketing, dissemination, and evaluation program to measure the use and educational value of these videotapes is being conducted at this time.

A list of CLR microforms, reprography, and nonprint media projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Society for Information Science , partial support of videotaping the technical sessions of the society's annual meeting held in Washington, D. C., October 23-26, 1972.	\$ 7,500	\$ 5,000
Governors State University , to assist its Learning Resources Center in a pilot project to develop, test, and evaluate an economical system for using selectively disseminated microfiche from the National Technical Information Service.	5,138	1,400
Mega System Design, Ltd. , for development of an automatic library card camera. [\$23,400 - 1972]	—————	5,850
Microfiche Reader Testing Device Project (CLR-administered), for the development of a booklet on reader selection and of a small set of microfiche to enable librarians to determine inexpensively and reliably the suitability of any microfiche reader for their purposes.	10,650	1,825
New York Public Library , to determine the feasibility of putting the NYPL Research Libraries' retrospective and prospective catalogs on microfilm. [\$10,000 - 1971]	(\$1,669)	2,331
MICROFORMS, REPROGRAPHY TOTALS, 1972-73	\$ 21,619	\$ 16,406

preservation and library technology

The Council's preservation and conservation activities on a national level—support of the W. J. Barrow Laboratory, the Library of Congress' Preservation Research Office, and various American Library Association (ALA) projects—were complemented in 1972-73 with a two-year matching grant of \$70,300 to the New England Interstate Library Compact (a political subdivision of the governments of Maine, New Hampshire, Vermont, Massachusetts, Connecticut, and Rhode Island) for the establishment of the New England Document Conservation Center.

New England Document Conservation Center

The Center will draw heavily on the proven techniques developed by Barrow and others and largely unavailable on a local level at this time. The enthusiasm and spirit of cooperation expressed for a facility of this sort by New England's librarians, archivists, and records officers is such that the consortium's officials are confident that the Conservation Center will be largely self-supporting at the end of the two-year Council grant.

Initially the Center will be a workshop where, on a fee basis, techniques of document preservation, repair, and restoration will be applied to materials submitted for treatment by institutions in the six states. As needs are demonstrated and if the workload permits, the services will be extended beyond New England. The Center will serve, if successful, as a model for other areas with similar needs.

The Barrow Laboratory

Since 1961, the Council has supported The Barrow Laboratory in its investigations of problems related to the preservation of books and other library materials and the development of paper standards.³³ The Laboratory's most significant work in the past year has been the further development of a gaseous diffusion process by which a number of books can be deacidified at the same time.

The Laboratory also completed a new set of specifications for permanent/durable (P/D) paper, and is making substantial progress in its work toward specifications for a coated P/D paper, the determination of maximum safe alkalinity for paper exposed to a range of chemical

³³ VII:20-23.

conditions, and the testing of groundwood content paper for P/D status.

A new grant was approved by the Council Board of Directors in April for continued operation of the Barrow Laboratory, for the period August 1, 1973, through June 30, 1974.

**Preservation
research
at Library
of Congress**

In its January 1973 "Semiannual Report on Developments at the Library of Congress," the *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* notes under preservation activities: "With a completely equipped, fully staffed laboratory, the Preservation Research Office is now directing its efforts to research."³⁴

The steps that led to this brief item go back to 1960 when the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) established a preservation committee. Then came the ensuing committee report, "The Preservation of Deteriorating Books," in 1964; a Council grant of \$26,800 to ARL to conduct the first phase of the Pilot Preservation Project at the Library of Congress in 1967; and a Council commitment of \$95,000 to the Library of Congress in 1970 toward equipping its Preservation Research Office.³⁵

While a number of research projects are now under way at the Library of Congress, major emphasis in the final six months of 1972 was given to coordinating information and research data on water-damaged books and manuscripts following Hurricane Agnes and the Temple University Library fire. The Restoration Office prepared a pamphlet entitled "Emergency Procedures for Salvaging Flood or Water-Damaged Library Materials," distributing it to over 600 U. S. libraries.

With the assistance of a grant from the National Endowment for the Arts, the Preservation Research Office sponsored a meeting of conservators and scientists in August to consider the problem of water-damaged materials. The immediate outgrowth was a crash program to investigate various drying methods for such materials and to identify optimum techniques for their salvage. A full report on this program will soon be published by the Library under the title, "Emergency Research Program on Methods of Drying Wet/Frozen Books."

**ALA's
Library
Technology
Reports**

Although the American Library Association's (ALA) Library Technology Program is no longer in existence, personnel concerned with ALA's *Library Technology Reports (LTR)* are monitoring several technology projects and promoting the program's published reports in the library press. *LTRs* are also exchanged with the National Reprographic Center for Documentation in England on a selective basis, with each group publishing some of the other's reports.

³⁴ "Semiannual Report on Developments at the Library of Congress," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 32 (January 19, 1973).

³⁵ XVI:41-42.

Included in the *LTR* projects are three sponsored by the Council: (1) performance testing of plastic card catalog trays with wood fronts (reported on in November *LTR* as a "good compromise" between wood and plastic trays), (2) evaluation of the effectiveness of film rejuvenation treatments, and (3) performance testing of a new low-cost catalog card cabinet.

A list of CLR preservation and library technology projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for performance testing of plastic card catalog trays with wood fronts. [\$10,220—1972]	\$———	\$ 4,610
American Library Association , to evaluate the effectiveness of film rejuvenation treatments. [\$3,709—1972]	—————	—————
American Library Association , for performance testing of a new low-cost catalog card cabinet. [\$4,015—1972]	—————	1,750
American Library Association , toward preparation and issuance by the Library Technology Program of five publications that will constitute a comprehensive manual on the care and repair of books and other library materials. [\$30,000—1968]	—————	1,439
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , continued operation of the laboratory for the period August 16, 1971, to July 31, 1973. [\$265,350—1972]	—————	119,347
Anthony Cains , to complete a workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts based on the practices of the Restoration Department of Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, Italy. [\$4,350—1972]	43	1,922
Margaret Hey , to investigate book and archival paper restoration techniques along scientific lines already under way in Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome, Italy. [\$10,500—1972]	—————	3,508
Levittown Public Library , to test the effectiveness of an electronic book-theft detection system. [\$8,990—1971]	—————	990
Library of Congress , assistance in equipping a preservation research office in the Library. [\$95,000—1970]	—————	—————
New England Interstate Library Compact , to assist that six-state consortium to establish the New England Document Conservation Center.	70,300	6,250
Royal College of Art (London), for the study of early limp vellum binding practices for purposes of conservation. [\$9,720—1970]	—————	(\$142)
PRESERVATION AND TECHNOLOGY TOTALS, 1972-73	\$ 70,343	\$139,674

international cooperation

Library activities are fundamentally the same the world over. Librarians—no matter where they are or what language they speak—are agreed about their functions, use more or less the same procedures in carrying them out and the same terms to describe them. There are indeed large differences, from country to country, in levels of requirements and the methods employed to meet them. But the degree of community of interest far exceeds any differences, and techniques and procedures, no matter where they are developed, are to a significant extent transferable. Thus cooperation on an international level is vital—as much for the most sophisticated systems as for those in earlier stages of development.

The Council's charter commitment to "improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives" took a variety of forms in 1972-73 and touched directly or indirectly libraries throughout the world. Much of this activity involved Council staff; a significant part was conducted through the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA); and a third portion was in the form of financial assistance to important international conferences.

International Federation of Library Associations

In its first 15 years, CLR invested its limited funds available for international activities in dozens of diverse projects and organizations. Although much of significance was accomplished in this way, by 1970 it had become apparent to the Council that the most effective road to

international cooperation among librarians and library systems lay within an organization in which representatives of many countries, including the United States, participated on an equal basis. The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) was the logical vehicle.

Founded in 1927, and with consultative status in UNESCO, IFLA had played an important part as the main international forum for the discussion of library problems. But it lacked the resources to become the effective organization it could and should be, both to meet the growing expectations of the international library community and to deal from a position of strength with other groups in allied fields.

The Council therefore concluded that the most useful long-term contribution it could make to international cooperation among libraries would be to assist IFLA in developing its potential for professional leadership. This decision came at a time when IFLA itself, after a period of self-examination, had determined that its influence would be greatly increased if it were able to maintain a capable permanent staff which could effectively carry forward the ongoing activities of the organization. To achieve this, IFLA decided to restructure its dues and thus increase its income and its ability to support a secretariat. A grant made by the Council in 1971, to be paid over a three-year period, is enabling IFLA to move toward this objective in the transitional years until the new dues schedule becomes fully implemented.³⁶

**IFLA
Committee
on
Cataloguing**

The Council's first important international venture had to do with cataloging, the process which arranges the information in a library so that it may be readily found by or for the user. In this as in all the processes employed by libraries to serve their users, uniformity of practice is not only desirable but essential. For now more than ever scholarship recognizes no geographic boundaries, and its requirements are truly international in scope.

IFLA had for several years been working on the coordination of cataloging practices when the Council in 1958 provided that organization with funds for a preliminary meeting to make careful plans for the 1961 International Conference on Cataloging Principles in Paris, which was also supported by the Council.³⁷ The Paris Conference was attended by more than 100 participants from 53 countries (with over 100 observers from 20 countries), and resulted in a substantial measure of agreement in an area where agreement had previously seemed almost impossible. The Conference report was widely circulated and contributed greatly to the present successful progress toward coordination of cataloging practices in many parts of the world.

A further grant in 1969 enabled the IFLA Committee on Uniform Cataloguing Rules to organize a meeting of specialists in Copenhagen to review developments since the 1961 Conference and to examine the

³⁶ XVI:37-38.

³⁷ IV:13, 23.

prospects for further advances through standardization and mechanization. Significant progress was made at this meeting toward agreement on standards of bibliographical description for catalog entries.³⁸

It had by this time become clear that the important activities of the committee would move more quickly and efficiently with the help of a permanent staff. In June 1971 the Council made a three-year grant for the establishment and support of a secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing, to furnish needed continuity and coordination of its important work.³⁹ *International Cataloguing*, published quarterly by the secretariat at a modest subscription rate, provides a forum for feedback and discussion as well as dissemination of information about worldwide planning for and development of cataloging standards. The sharing of cataloging between countries and institutions, now rendered more feasible and in some ways more complex by the adoption of computerized procedures, has been materially advanced by these developments.

**Universal
Bibliographic
Control**

In a January 31, 1973, paper presented at the American Library Association Midwinter Conference, Dorothy Anderson, executive secretary of the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing, reviewed activities in the areas of international standardization of cataloging and bibliographical records. She stated the situation well: "There are two sides to this issue. First comes the acceptance of international standards for producing bibliographical records so that each country can contribute in a form which will be acceptable to all others. Secondly is the recognition that the national bibliographic agency in each country is for its own authors the authority for determining the form of the author's name, whether it is personal or corporate, and that the descriptive records it produces are acceptable to all countries as the definitive record of its publication. This is all part of our larger ideal of an integrated worldwide international communication system, the concept of universal bibliographic control (UBC)."

Fully endorsing this broad ideal, the Council three years ago authorized its chief systems staff member to keep in touch with and assist in matters relating to its furtherance. He in turn works closely with Council consultants Sir Frank Francis (former president and now honorary president of IFLA and director-emeritus of the British Museum) and Herman Liebaers (president of IFLA and director of the Royal Library of Belgium), both long-term advocates of UBC. "Universal Bibliographic Control" is the theme of the 1973 IFLA annual conference in Grenoble, France, August 27-September 1, 1973.

**IFLA
annual
meetings**

At the 1972 IFLA annual conference in Budapest, Hungary, August 26-September 2, 1972, "Reading in a Changing World" was the theme, selected in support of UNESCO's proclamation of 1972 as "International

³⁸ XIV:42.

³⁹ XVI:38.

Book Year." It was at this conference that Foster Mohrhardt, the Council's senior program officer and for six years a board member and officer of IFLA, received a special award from the organization in recognition of his service and contribution to international librarianship.

In November 1974, IFLA will hold its 40th annual conference in Washington, D. C. The Council has made a \$10,000 grant to IFLA to help in making this meeting one that will have a significant impact on the international development of librarianship. The funds will in part support a Washington-based secretariat responsible for handling the necessary work leading up to the meeting.

International Book Year

The Council's partial support of a secretariat for United States participation in International Book Year (IBY) helped this country to initiate and take part in a host of activities of interest to the national and international library community in 1972. In her *Summary Report* on the year's activities, Esther J. Walls, director of the U. S. Secretariat, International Book Year 1972, reported on 124 IBY activities in six broad categories which occurred in 1972.⁴⁰ The Council also assisted the IBY efforts by contributing additional support to two of these activities: (1) an international conference on the role of library services and educational materials in developing countries at Mohonk Mountain House in New Paltz, N.Y., December 10-13, 1972, in cooperation with the Administration for International Development, and (2) an Inter-American Seminar on Libraries, Archives, and Documentation in Washington, D. C., November 6-17, 1972, in cooperation with the Organization of American States, the U. S. State Department, the American Library Association, and the U. S. National Commission for Unesco. Council staff participated in both meetings.

The "Mohonk Statement"

In what has been termed the "Mohonk Statement," it was agreed by the participants in the New Paltz meeting that "developing countries need not only the capacity to create and produce materials—not only to write and print books—but also to make them realistically available to each student or reader. Effective use of books in schools and a vigorous system of free libraries are both essential to this availability . . . Readers cannot be created by instruction alone; they must have material to read that is relevant to the deep purposes of their lives." The statement calls for "a planned, a determined, a realistic, and a zealous effort on the part of developed and developing countries and international agencies working together, to move toward providing for the people of all the world a generous access to books that can help open for them the doors to a more abundant and a more meaningful future."

⁴⁰ Esther J. Walls, *International Book Year 1972, Summary Report* (New York: National Book Committee, 1973).

**Inter-
American
seminars**

Two Council-assisted Inter-American seminars of significance to librarians took place in 1972-73. The first was held in Washington, D. C., November 6-17, 1972, in connection with International Book Year. Its subject: "Integrated Information Services of Libraries, Archives and Documentation Centers in Latin America and the Caribbean." Organized by the American Library Association in cooperation with the Organization of American States, it succeeded in communicating to participants the "need to integrate the services of libraries, archives and documentation centers, first on a national and then on an international basis, into a unified system, even though the degree to which such a system may be a voluntary network of component parts will vary from country to country."

The second seminar was held in Colombia, February 12-13, 1973. It dealt with centralized cataloging and the use of MARCAL (MARC for Latin America), and the Council provided funds for participation by *Choice* editor Richard Gardner and by Paul Miles, assistant librarian of the University of California at Los Angeles (UCLA). In the final report to CLR the coordinator of the meeting observed: "Dr. Gardner's practical advice based on his experience working with Books for College Libraries and *Choice* was invaluable in developing the specific modus operandi for LILIBU (List of Books For Use in Latin American Universities). Mr. Miles served as chairman of the working group on MARCAL. His extensive experience in the technical aspects of library organization, both in the use of MARC tapes at UCLA, and recently as head of a California task force concerned with the derivation of cataloging information from MARC tapes, was drawn upon throughout the meeting."

**U. S.-
Japanese
Conference**

Once again the Council provided funds for a U. S.-Japanese Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education (the second). The meeting, supported also by the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Johnson Foundation, was held at Wingspread, the conference center of the Johnson Foundation in Racine, Wisconsin, on October 7-20, 1972. In final action at the conference it was resolved by some 100 librarians in attendance that cooperative projects involving bibliographical control, qualitative surveys of collections, and the like be further implemented; that assistance for the development of collections for the study of Japan in the United States be sought from appropriate Japanese foundations and other institutions; that small working committees be organized to plan the implementation of specific projects; and that a third conference be convened in Japan in 1975.⁴¹

In July 1972, a useful publication by ALA, *University and Research Libraries in Japan and the United States*, based on proceedings of the first U. S.-Japanese Conference held in Tokyo in May 1969, was published by the American Library Association.

⁴¹ XIII:31-32.

A list of CLR international cooperation projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association (ALA) , partial support of UNESCO seminar on integrated information services of libraries, archives, and documentation centers in Latin America and the Caribbean.	\$ 2,196	\$ 2,196
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , support of a secretariat to plan and organize the 1974 IFLA annual conference to be held in Washington, D. C.	10,000	—————
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , travel funds for the speakers participating in the 1972 symposium, "Reading in a Changing World," at the August 1972 General Meeting. [\$1,500—1972]	(\$450)	1,050
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , to enable IFLA to institute reforms and operate at an effective professional level during the three years required to complete restructuring of dues so that the organization may become self-supporting. [\$100,000—1971]	—————	32,000
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , to establish a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing as a center to promote and coordinate the international standardization of cataloging practices. [\$54,000—1971]	—————	16,800
National Book Committee, Inc. , partial support of a conference on the role of library services and educational materials in educational programs in developing countries.	9,000	6,500
National Book Committee, Inc. , partial support of a secretariat for the United States' participation in International Book Year. [\$25,000—1972]	—————	15,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as matching funds toward CLR-NEH \$15,376 grant to ALA Advisory Commission for Liaison with Japanese Libraries toward support of Second U. S.-Japan Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education.	7,688	7,688
Organization of American States , for travel funds to enable two U. S. librarians to attend and advise a planning meeting devoted to a list of books for Latin American university libraries (LILIBU) and centralized cataloging (CATACEN).	1,391	1,391
Travel Funds , to enable librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to attend meetings abroad where they have significant roles to play. [\$5,000—1971; \$5,000—1972]	(\$45)	2,750
Travel Funds , to enable important foreign librarians to visit the United States, when their presence is essential for the purpose of carrying out selected tasks. [\$5,000—1970]	—————	150
INTERNATIONAL TOTALS, 1972-73	\$ 29,780	\$ 85,525

archives and special collections

Archives and special collections constitute an important segment of the broader library world's responsibilities. Although archivists and curators of special collections are primarily concerned with preservation of the record and the building of complete collections, their problems are in many ways also those of librarians who can often profit greatly from the preservation and collection efforts of others.

During the year 14 projects were active in this area. They involved special collections in law, music, art, Chinese studies, U. S. studies, and social sciences; related archival aids such as the collection, care, and use of photographs, the care of manuscripts, and filming standards for reproduction of rare materials; and information on orientalists and Russian regional archives.

Two books resulting from CLR grants were published during the year:

Directory of Music Research Libraries, Part III: Spain, France, Italy, Portugal, edited by Rita Benton, The University of Iowa, Iowa City, Iowa 52240, 342 pp., includes material on over 500 libraries in the four countries. A CLR officer's grant partially defrayed Dr. Benton's expenses incurred in visiting some of the more important libraries.

International Cooperation in Orientalist Librarianship, edited by Enid Bishop and Jean M. Waller, National Library of Australia, Canberra, Australia, 284 pp., is based on a series of library seminars at the 28th International Congress of Orientalists in Canberra, Australia, January 6-12, 1971. It is the hope of the editors that "the practical emphasis of the papers will stimulate further efforts and promote greater cooperation in the field of acquisitions and of the bibliographic control of materials."

A list of CLR archives and special collections projects active in 1972-73 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Association for State and Local History , toward the preparation of a book on the collection, care and use of photographs. [\$10,000 - 1972]	\$———	\$———

American Association of State and Local History , for the preparation of a manual on the care of manuscript collections. [\$34,604 – 1970]	—————	15,000
American Association of Law Libraries , to conduct an annual statistical survey of law library resources in the United States and Canada [\$20,000 – 1968]	—————	2,000
Etta Arntzen , for a revision of the original 1959 edition of Mary W. Chamberlin's <i>Guide to Art Reference Books</i> . [\$8,000 – 1971]	—————	—————
Australian National Library , to assist in the travel of Asian librarians to the 28th International Congress of Orientalists in Canberra, Australia, and the publication of papers presented. [\$20,000 – 1971]	—————	—————
Dartmouth College , for the coordination of a program for producing microfilm editions of rare research materials. [\$8,800 – 1970]	—————	4,800
Institute of United States Studies (London) , toward a preliminary survey of the market for an American Studies bibliography. [\$5,000 – 1971]	—————	3,300
National Central Library (London) , toward the support of continued publication and increased distribution of acquisition lists of American titles for loan in the United Kingdom. [\$15,000 – 1970]	(\$1,490)	(\$490)
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as matching grant to NEH for a program at Stanford University to achieve bibliographic control of secondary literature relevant to modern Chinese society. [\$5,000 – 1970]	—————	—————
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as matching grant to NEH toward the preparation of a projected directory entitled: "Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids" by Patricia K. Grimsted . [\$12,739 – 1971]	—————	—————
Rare Books Conference on Facsimiles , to enable Filming Standards Subcommittee members to attend two meetings to produce a set of physical standards for reproduction of materials held by member libraries. [\$2,000 – 1971]	(\$713)	126
Society of American Archivists , toward the expenses of a committee to examine the programs of the Society in an effort to improve its service to members and to scholars. [\$3,500 – 1971]	—————	1,000
University of California at San Diego , to assist in the preparation of 2nd edition of <i>Sources of Information in the Social Sciences</i> . [\$4,910 – 1970]	—————	2,894
University of Iowa , to undertake an investigation of the administration, services, and collections of music libraries in Spain, Portugal, France, and England. The finished product was Part III of a <i>Directory of Music Research Libraries</i> . [\$1,425 – 1971]	(\$325)	(\$3)
ARCHIVES, SPECIAL COLLECTIONS TOTALS, 1972-73	(\$ 2,528)	\$ 28,627

professional development

It is the professional librarians who most affect, and are affected by, the growth and change under way in the library world. Yet, while their responsibilities and need for current knowledge in a dozen or more areas have expanded continuously for a quarter century, their opportunities for professional advancement and self-enrichment have not increased to any significant degree. As a first step in attempting to provide these opportunities the Council on Library Resources launched two programs in 1968: (1) surveys of the compensation structures of professional librarians in colleges and universities, and (2) the CLR Fellowship Program for midcareer librarians. The surveys have shown clearly that academic librarians fare considerably less well than faculty in terms of salary and such benefits as leaves of absence. The fellowship program has enabled academic librarians, and others as well, to improve themselves professionally while pursuing approved projects of their own choosing while on a continuous leave of absence of from three to twelve months.

Third survey of academic librarians

The third survey of the compensation structure of professional librarians in colleges and universities, for 1972-73, has been completed and, as with previous ones, is being analyzed by Donald Cameron and Peggy Heim. The first survey covered the academic year 1969-70; the second, for the period 1970-71 indicated an upward swing in the number of subject specialists in academic libraries.⁴²

Particular emphasis has been given this year to the economic situation of nonsubject specialists in academic libraries, most of whom are in such management areas as fiscal planning and control, personnel, systems operations, computer services, and the like. Information on the potential financial rewards for this kind of specialist has been collected via the 1972-73 questionnaire and is presently undergoing the interpretation process prior to publication.

⁴² Donald Cameron and Peggy Heim, *How Well Are They Paid, 1970-71* (Washington: Council on Library Resources, 1972).

Thirty-three library and archive professionals received Council fellowships in 1972-73. An analysis of this fifth class of CLR Fellows sheds considerable light on trends in the library profession. For example, a fair proportion of the recipients hold positions in the growing curator-bibliographer-specialist category noted by Cameron and Heim in their February 1972 report. The studies to be undertaken by the Fellows are as diverse as their titles. At least three are intended to result in books, and it is expected that, as in previous years, many of the others will also result in some form of publication.

The 33 fellowship awards bring to 115 the total announced by the Council since 1969.⁴³ Librarians working in 30 of the 50 states plus the District of Columbia, Canada, and Nigeria have been recipients.

The 33 recipients of Council on Library Resources fellowships in 1972-73 and their projects are as follows:

Shelah Bell, Assistant Director of Libraries, El Paso (Texas) Public Library. An internship in public library management.

George S. Bobinski, Dean, School of Information and Library Studies, State University of New York at Buffalo. A survey and analysis of the present status and future trends of library science doctoral programs in the U. S. and Canada.

Mary B. Cassata, Assistant Director of University Libraries for Public Service, State University of New York at Buffalo. A study of the implementation problem of full faculty status for librarians.

Charles Kwang Hsiang Chen, Far East Specialist, Dartmouth College Library. To conduct a search of rare materials from the T'ang, Sung, Yuan, Ming, and Ch'ing dynasties, and also of works by many contemporary Chinese authors to meet the final requirements of the *Biographical and Bibliographical Dictionary of Chinese Authors*.

Phyllis Dain, Associate Professor of Library Service, Columbia University. To conduct research on "The New York Public Library: A History, 1913-1970," the second volume of a two-volume work on the history of the library from its founding in 1895 to the present.

Richard Dionne, Head, Science and Technology Libraries, Syracuse University. An internship in university library management.

James Beaupre Dodd, Associate Professor and Information Consultant, Georgia Institute of Technology Library. To study the demands being made by business and industrial organizations for library services from universities and colleges and the effects these demands are having on the libraries.

H. Paul Dove, Librarian, Erskine College (S.C.). A study of addition/renovation projects in college and university library construction since 1967.

Allan Judge Dyson, Head, Moffitt Undergraduate Library, University of California, Berkeley. To study, compare, and evaluate programs of undergraduate library instruction at large universities in the United States and England.

⁴³ XVI:46-48; XV:17-19; XIV:44-46; XIII:41-42; XII:35

Fern L. Edwards, Reference Librarian and Associate Professor of Library Science, Gallaudet College (D. C.). To devise a system of individual access to non-book information which will serve the needs of deaf students at Gallaudet College.

G. Edward Evans, Associate Professor, School of Library Service, University of California, Los Angeles. A study of the Scandinavian system of library education to determine whether such systems have some applicability to the American system.

Esther Greenberg, Chief Cataloger and Assistant Head of Technical Services, Case Western Reserve University Libraries. To study innovative systems for acquisitions and cataloging in selected individual libraries and library networks in order to apply them toward designing a new pattern of work flow.

Theodore G. Grieder, Jr., Curator, Division of Special Collections, New York University Libraries. To complete an acquisitions manual directed toward librarians and professors at college, university, and research libraries.

Ira Whitney Harris, Assistant Dean, Graduate School of Library Studies, University of Hawaii. A study of current information retrieval practices in automated libraries to determine the educational requirements for librarians occupying public service positions in these institutions.

Helen Arlene Howard, University Librarian, Sir George Williams University (Canada). A study of the organizational structures of those universities in Canada and the United States which have concentrated under one administrative head information services of at least two units.

Brigitte L. Kenney, Assistant Professor, Graduate School of Library Science, Drexel University (Pa.). To assess the status of cable communication activities in the libraries of the United States and Canada.

Donald M. Koslow, Executive Officer, Library and Information Systems, University of Massachusetts. To investigate the effect that the development of computer-based centralized processing is having on academic library networks.

Robert French Lewis, Biomedical Librarian, Biomedical Library, University of California, San Diego. A study of medical Festschriften and their reference content.

Karl Lo, Head of the Asiatic Collection, University of Washington Library. To survey and analyze the cataloging needs of Chinese language materials in American research libraries.

Avinash C. Maheshwary, South Asia Librarian, Duke University Library. A study of government publications of the developing countries of South Asia in the United States: present status and future trends.

John A. McCrossan, Coordinator of Interlibrary Cooperation, State of Pennsylvania, Harrisburg, Pa. To study a number of programs of interlibrary cooperation and coordination in order to get an overview of what is happening and to determine what factors seem to be related to successful programs.

Robert S. McGee, Assistant Systems Development Librarian, University of Chicago Library. To gather data on the history, status, and potential of computer-based library systems with on-line bibliographic files.

John B. McTaggart, Director, Library Services, Methodist Theological School, Delaware, Ohio. To study the evolution and continuing program of the Graduate Theological Union Library in Berkeley, California.

Robert Carl Miller, Associate Director of Reader Services, University of Chicago Library. To examine patterns of science library organization and service to researchers within the universities and their relationships to other available information resources.

Carlton C. Rochell, Librarian, Atlanta Public Library. To research and design criteria for a role for urban public libraries in nontraditional study programs, with emphasis on adequacy of resources and the sources and adequacy of finance.

Hal B. Schell, Associate Director of Libraries, University of Cincinnati. To survey, study, and analyze the planning of physical facilities for academic libraries for the integration of services made possible by advances in educational communications technology.

Dorothy May Schmidt Obi, Sub-Librarian, University of Nigeria. To study comparatively the curriculum for professional librarianship in Sub-Saharan Africa in order to establish direction for curriculum development in next 10 years.

Russell Shank, Director of Libraries, Smithsonian Institution (D. C.). To assess the potential of new developments in telecommunications to facilitate library functions, and to identify and detail the issues that must be faced in order to insure optimum utility and utilization of telecommunications by libraries.

Thomas Shaughnessy, Director, Dana Library, Rutgers University, Newark, N.J. To measure and evaluate the response of urban university libraries to educationally disadvantaged students.

Barbara Eggleston Smith, Documents Librarian, Skidmore College (N.Y.). A study of British official publications in terms of mechanisms involved in their publication and distribution, their scope and substance, and their accessibility to and utilization by the various communities of interest.

Francis F. Spreitzer, Head, Micrographics and Reprography Department, University of Southern California. A field study of library microform systems in a cross-section of academic, research, and public libraries, examining the relationships among programs, collections, services, facilities, staff, and populations served.

Sarah Katherine Thomson, Chairman, Library and Learning Resources Department, Bergen Community College (N.J.). Independent study and investigation of the application of modern techniques of management to the operation of community college library learning resource centers for improved skills in administration.

John William Weatherford, Director of Libraries, Central Michigan University. To gather documents and interview persons in order to study the effect of collective bargaining on academic libraries.

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM TOTALS, 1972-1973	\$103,745	\$ 64,215

**grants and contracts
payments totals
1972-73**

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES	\$ 24,958	\$ 36,833
AUTOMATION AND NETWORKS	296,999	265,049
THE ACADEMIC LIBRARY	148,485	282,975
THE PUBLIC LIBRARY	133,700	48,500
ARCHIVES AND SPECIAL COLLECTIONS	(2,528)	28,627
INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION	29,780	85,525
MICROFORMS, REPROGRAPHY, NONPRINT MEDIA	21,619	16,406
PRESERVATION AND LIBRARY TECHNOLOGY	70,343	139,674
COUNCIL FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM	103,745	64,215
	<hr/>	<hr/>
GRAND TOTALS	\$827,101	\$967,804

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 21, 1973

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1973 and June 30, 1972, the expenses, income and changes in fund balance and the changes in cash and investments for the years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

**Statement of Assets,
Liabilities and Fund Balance**

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	June 30	
	1973	1972
ASSETS		
Cash	\$ 115,314	\$ 225,138
Investments		
Savings account (Note 3)	10,595	11,964
Certificates of deposit, at cost	800,000	250,000
Commercial promissory notes, at cost	200,000	
Accrued interest receivable	2,219	63
Accrued royalty income receivable	696	1,083
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 1)	1,976,461	3,976,461
Prepaid expenses and deposits	1,676	1,921
	<u>\$3,106,961</u>	<u>\$4,466,630</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Grants and contracts payable	\$1,426,792	\$1,603,170
Fellowships payable	103,725	89,155
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	30,479	27,885
	<u>1,560,996</u>	<u>1,720,210</u>
Fund balance (Note 2)	1,545,965	2,746,420
	<u>\$3,106,961</u>	<u>\$4,466,630</u>

Statement of Expenses, Income and Changes in Fund Balance

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1973	1972
EXPENSES		
Program		
Grants and contracts	\$ 736,850	\$2,121,797
Fellowships	103,745	80,041
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants and fellowships awarded	<u>(34,619)</u>	<u>(71,319)</u>
	805,976	2,130,519
Compensation and employee benefits	177,039	163,003
Consultants' fees and expenses	30,848	40,096
Travel	17,819	16,780
Other	<u>3,760</u>	<u>3,729</u>
	<u>1,035,442</u>	<u>2,354,127</u>
Administrative		
Compensation and employee benefits	126,785	110,763
Rent	24,783	21,930
Professional services	10,019	7,005
Travel and meetings	14,802	11,407
Furniture and equipment	2,156	3,137
Printing and duplication	7,829	9,343
Office and other expense	<u>16,862</u>	<u>16,438</u>
	<u>203,236</u>	<u>180,023</u>
	<u>1,238,678</u>	<u>2,534,150</u>
INCOME FROM INVESTMENTS	36,462	21,234
INCOME FROM ROYALTIES (Note 3)	1,761	3,325
SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTED CONTRACT (Note 4)		<u>6,500</u>
	<u>38,223</u>	<u>31,059</u>
EXCESS OF EXPENSES OVER INCOME	(1,200,455)	(2,503,091)
Fund balance, beginning of year	2,746,420	249,511
Add-Grant from The Ford Foundation (Note 1)		<u>5,000,000</u>
Fund balance, end of year (Note 2)	<u>\$1,545,965</u>	<u>\$2,746,420</u>

Statement of Changes in Cash and Investments

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1973	1972
CASH RECEIPTS		
Receipts from The Ford Foundation	\$2,000,000	\$2,084,574
Income from investments and royalties	36,454	29,293
Grant, fellowship and other refunds	4,201	15,925
	<u>2,040,655</u>	<u>2,129,792</u>
CASH DISBURSEMENTS		
Program expense	1,198,014	1,974,560
Administrative expense	203,784	186,893
Employee travel advances	50	100
	<u>1,401,848</u>	<u>2,161,553</u>
Increase (decrease)	638,807	(31,761)
Increase (decrease) in accrued interest	2,156	(46)
Cash and investments, beginning of year	487,165	518,972
Cash and investments, end of year	<u>\$1,128,128</u>	<u>\$ 487,165</u>

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

1. The Ford Foundation Grants

Effective July 1, 1971, The Ford Foundation approved an additional \$5,000,000 grant to the Council for the continuation and expansion of the Council's program. The new grant agreement specifies that the remaining balance of a prior grant and the new grant are to be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of approximately \$2,000,000 for a three year period beginning July 1, 1971.

2. Appropriations of Fund Balance

At June 30, 1973, and June 30, 1972 \$569,360 and \$389,903, respectively, had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts. In addition, at those dates \$95,000 and \$94,150, respectively, had been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each to be made at his discretion.

3. Royalties

On October 10, 1969, the Council entered an agreement for the publication of "Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries" developed under its sponsorship. Royalties received from the sale of the original publication are being used to fund the preparation of a revision and supplement to this work.

4. Settlement of Disputed Contract

In fiscal year 1972 the Council received \$6,500 in settlement of their claim against a grantee for an uncompleted contract.

5. Commitments

The Council leases office space under a lease expiring November 30, 1977 providing for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$26,220.

Index to active CLR projects, 1972-73

In the fiscal year 1972-73 the Council on Library Resources made 24 new grants for projects and monitored 68 others which had been funded in earlier years. An index of institutional recipients cited in this report follows:

- Administration and Management Research
 - Association of New York City, Inc. 33
- American Association for State and Local History 46, 47
- American Association of Law Libraries 47
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- American Society for Information Science 36
- Arntzen, Etta 47
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- Australian National Library 47
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- Brown University (see NEH) 29
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- CLR administered programs 20, 36
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- Howard University (see NEH) 29
- Indiana State University 34
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- International Federation of Library Associations 45
- Jackson State College (see NEH) 29
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- Swarthmore College (see NEH) 29
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- United States Book Exchange 13
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- University of Chicago (see NEH) 20
- University of Colorado (see NEH) 29
- University of Iowa 47
- University of Lancaster (England) 29
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- University of Richmond (see NEH) 29
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- Washington State Library 21

Acknowledgements

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